

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети №1-сон Акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Акбаров Миршавкат Мирлоимович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, В.Ваҳидов номидаги
Республика ихтисослаштирилган жарроҳлик маркази*

Саидов Садамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергандовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталя Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
Акушерства и гинекологии №1 Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

доктор медицинских наук,
Республиканский специализированный центр
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова

Саидов Саидмир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
Samarkand State Medical University No.1
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine,
Tashkent Medical Academy
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Akbarov Mirshavkat Mirolimovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Republican Specialized Center of Surgery
named after academician V.Vakhidov*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Urinbaeva A. Nilufar, Abduganieva F. Dilsuz**
THE PROBLEM OF FETAL GROWTH RETRACTION SYNDROME IN OBSTETRICS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....10

THERAPY

2. **Jakbarova A. Mohida Juraeva A. Mohigul**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA.....22
3. **Boltaev J. Kamol, Rizaeva J. Malika**
THE ROLE OF PREDICTORS IN THE FORMATION OF THROMBOSIS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION (REVIEW ARTICLE).....27
4. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Akhmedova A. Gulchekhra**
THE ROLE OF ANTIFILAGGRIN ANTIBODIES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AT AN EARLY STAGE.....33
5. **Akhmedova Sh. Nilufar, Rizayeva J. Malika**
CHANGES IN ANTITHROMBIN INDICATORS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION.....39
6. **Agababyan R. Irina, Djabbarova M. Nafisa**
CURRENT ISSUES IN MODERN TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....44
7. **Abdushukurova R. Komila, Akhmedov A. Ibrat**
FOUNDATIONS OF IMMUNOPATHOGENESIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....55
8. **Makhatmuradova N.Nargiza**
FEATURES OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN NONSPECIFIC INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA.....66
9. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Eshmuratov E. Sardor**
FEATURES OF THE SUBPOPULATION COMPOSITION OF PERIPHERAL BLOOD LYMPHOCYTES IN THE FIRST PERIODS OF THE DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....73
10. **Kityan S.Aleksandr**
COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....78

SURGERY

11. **Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arziev A Ismoil, Arzieva B Gulnora**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....83
12. **Zohidova H Sanoat, Mamataliyev R. Abdumalik**
DESPITE THE COMPLEXITY AND SERIOUSNESS OF THE DISEASE, MODERN TREATMENT METHODS CAN ACHIEVE POSITIVE RESULTS AND IMPROVE THE PROGNOSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....91
13. **Achilov T. Mirzakarim, Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Mirmuxammedov Dj.Nasimjon, Shakulov M. Azizbek**
INTRAGENATION OF PROLOSED RECTUM (CASE FROM PRACTICE).....97

14. **Babajanov S. Akhmadjon, Akhmedov I. Adkham, Shamsiev J. Shokhzod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE INTRAOPERATIVE THYROMETRY METHOD IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BENIGN THYROID GLAND PATHOLOGIES.....104
15. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
USE OF TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF STARGED ANTERIOR HERNIA ABDOMINAL WALL (LITERATURE REVIEW).....113
16. **Avazov A. Abdurakhim., Shakirov M. Bobur., Hakimov A. Erkin**
TREATMENT OF ISOLATED BURNS OF THE HAND AND FOOT IN A HUMID ENVIRONMENT WITH SILVER-CONTAINING PREPARATIONS.....120

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

17. **Fozilov A. Uktam**
DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS USING A COMPUTER PROGRAM.....126
18. **Nurova N. Shoxsanam**
THE INCIDENCE OF CHRONIC DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE WITH BREAST CANCER.....136
19. **Ibragimova Kh. Malika, Ruzikulova Sh. Munira**
PERIODONTAL STATUS ACCORDING TO THE CPITN INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH FATTY HEPATOSIS.....141
20. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Rakhimov Kh. Jahongir.**
INFLUENCE OF MAGNETOTHERAPY ON VARIOUS SYSTEMS OF THE BODY AND ON THE PROCESS OF WOUND HEALING IN CHILDREN WITH CLEFT LIP.....149
21. **Gaffarov A. Sunnatullo, Astanov M. Otabek**
DENTAL CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHIATRIC PATHOLOGIES.....154
22. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Mamedova Sh. Nigina**
EVALUATION OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF ODONTOGENIC PURULENT INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE JAWS.....161
23. **Agababyan R. Irina, Ismoilov M. Rajabboy**
SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN ATHEROSCLEROSIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS.....166
24. **Boymuradov A. Shukhrat, Ruzibayev R. Dilshod**
RESULTS OF ELIMINATING OF PERFORATION OF THE MAXILLARY SINUS BOTTOM USING PRF.....173
25. **Abasniya R. Surayyo**
LABORATORY INDICATORS OF IMPROVING METHODS OF TREATING PERIODONTITIS AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM REGION.....182
26. **Eronov Q. Yoqub**
THE INFLUENCE OF PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE MICROBIOCENOSIS OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES ON ORAL HYGIENE IN CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES.....187

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

27. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Raupova M. Kamola, Boltayev I. Anvar**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ACOUSTIC REFLEX OF THE INTRA-EAR MUSCLES IN OCCUPATIONAL HEARING DISORDERS.....193

28. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF
CHRONIC INFLAMMATION OF THE MIDDLE EAR.....200
29. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Ne`matov S. O`ktam, Khamraev Kh. Farid**
LOBULAR CAPILLARY HAEMANGIOMA OF THE NASAL CAVITY DURING
PREGNANCY: A CLINICAL CASE.....209
30. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Dustboboyev S. Dilshod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SURGICAL APPROACH FOR CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE
MAXILLARY SINUS.....214

PEDIATRICS

31. **Rakhmatullaev A. Akmal, Terebaev A. Bilim, Mazhidov Kh. Temur**
MODERN VIEWS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT PAYRE'S SYNDROME IN
CHILDREN.....221
32. **Garifulina M. Lilya M., Goyibova S. Nargiza**
MICROALBUMINURIA AS AN INDICATOR OF METABOLIC DISORDERS IN
OBESITY CHILDREN.....227
33. **Yusupova U. Umida**
PECULIARITIES OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN EARLY CHILDREN WITH NON-SOCIAL
PNEUMONIA LIVING IN ECOLOGICAL REGIONS.....233
34. **Kuryazova M. Sharofat, Khudaynazarova R. Salomat**
FREQUENCY AND STRUCTURE OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY IN
CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS.....241

CHILDREN SURGERY

35. **Yuldashev A. Botir, Murodova D. Malika**
ASSESSMENT OF CARDIORENAL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE
NEPHRITIC SYNDROME.....247

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

36. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Khakimova Z. Sohuba**
BRAIN REGENERATION: STEM CELL THERAPY FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE
DISEASES.....255
37. **Kodirov A. Umid, Abdurakhimov Mukhiddin**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CHRONIC BRUCELLIOSIS.....262
38. **Kodirov A. Umid, Turdiev Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CASE OF HERPETIC INFECTION.....269
39. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN PATIENTS
WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME.....275
40. **Muminov A. Bekzod, Matmurodov J. Rustambek, Khalimova M. Khanifa, Nazarova F. Madinabonu, Umirova M. Surayyo.**
CHANGED LEVELS OF INTERLEUKIN-6 IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS
WITH COVID-19.....281
41. **Mirjuraev M. Elbek, Samiev S. Asliddin, Urakov U. Shokir**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH
COGNITIVE CHANGES IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL CIRCULATION DISEASES.....289

ONCOLOGY AND GEMATOLOGY

42. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Yusupbekov A. Abrorjon, Tuychiyev D. Otabek**
STUDY OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STAGES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE IN THE
EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTRIC CANCER.....296
43. **Abdiyev Kattabek Makhmatovich**
COMPLICATIONS OF PRIMARY MYELOFIBROSIS AND TACTICS OF THEIR
TREATMENT.....303
44. **Azimova A. Makhbuba, Nasirova K. Khurshedakhon**
THYROID DYSFUNCTION IN BREAST CANCER.....316

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

45. **Kamalova A. Yokutkhon, Sulaimonov Sh. Vakil**
FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF THERAPEUTIC PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN
PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....325

MORPHOLOGY

46. **Kuryazov K. Akbar, Olimov Sh. Siddik**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN ORTHOPEDIC STATUS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE
AGE.....331
47. **Khoshimov L. Bobur, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE AORTA IN EXPERIMENTAL METABOLIC
SYNDROME.....339
48. **Muzaffarova Sh. Nargiza, Sheryigitova I. Nigina, Azizov M. Mardon**
A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE HUMAN BODY.....346
49. **Abdusattarov A. Adahamjon Alisherovich, Juraeva A. Mohigul, Ashuralieva A. Mavlyuda.**
THE CONCEPT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....353
50. **Oripov S. Firdavs Suratovich, Eshkabilova T. Surayo**
IMPACT OF ENERGY DRINKS COMPONENTS ON THE HUMAN BODY AND ITS
COMPLICATIONS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....361
51. **RADJABOV B. Akhtam**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL
DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC
ALCOHOLISM.....368
52. **TILYABOV Ikram, USMANOV Ravshan**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED
BY STREPTOZOTOCIN.....373

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

53. **Tilyakov B. Aziz, Tilyakov A. Xasan, Ayozboev A. Zuhridin, Nabiyev A. Muhammadi**
CRITERIA FOR THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF COMBINED
CHEST INJURIES IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE.....383
54. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Nomozov N. Fazliddin**
OPTIMAL METHODS OF CARE FOR VICTIMS WITH COMBINED BONE AND
VASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....390
55. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Tilyakov A. Khasan**
ASSESSMENT OF X-RAY INDICATORS OF INSTABILITY OF THE DISTAL
RADIOULNARY JOINT IN CHILDREN.....401

56. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek**
 DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (SCIENTIFIC REVIEW).....408

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

57. **Iskandarov I. Alisher, Kaidarov A. Makhammadali**
 EXPERT ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATION CONTENT OF CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS DURING THERMAL EXPOSURE ETHYLENE GLYCOL.....414
58. **Turonov Bobur Sobir ugli, Iskandarov Alisher Iskandarovitch**
 VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY.....420
59. **Davranova E. Aziza, Toshmamatov Sh. Alimardon, Tashev Sh. Ulmas, Ganiev N. Sobirzhon, Kushbakov M. Akbar**
 FORENSIC CHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS.....425

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

60. **Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza, Yakubova S. Nigina, Mirzaeva U. Adolat**
 CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH TICK-BORNE RICKETSIOSIS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....434
61. **Achilova M. Matlyuba, Shodiyeva A. Dilafruz**
 ASSESSMENT OF THE SAFETY OF HIGHLY ACTIVE ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH HIV INFECTION.....448
62. **Imamova A. Ilmira**
 RELEVANCE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS.....453
63. **Allaberganova S. Zumrad, Karimova A. Maqsuda, Rajapov Y. Shahzod, Kurbanbaeva K. Dilnoza**
 STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND PROTEOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF YEAST-LIKE FUNGI OF THE GENUS CANDIDA.....461
64. **Oslanov A. Absamat, Kodirov F. Jonibek, Samibaeva Kh. Umida, Suyarov A. Ulugbek, Qozieva L. Dilobar, Djumanazarov N. Sardorbek, Boysunov Ch. Shokhzod**
 SOME ASPECTS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MEASLES IN CHILDREN UNDER ONE YEAR OF ONE YEAR.....467

OPHTHALMOLOGY

65. **Yusupov F. Azamat, Khusanbaev Sh. Khasanjon, Abdullaeva I. Saida.**
 COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR SOLUTION.....475
66. **Xamidullayev F. Firdavs. Normatova M. Nargiza Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin**
 EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF BROLUCIZUMAB IN TREATING DIABETIC MACULAR EDEMA.....482
67. **Karimova Kh. Muyassar, Ubaydullaev O. Sardor**
 CLINICAL CASE OF IOL IMPLANTATION IN POSTVITRECTOMY EYE WITH APHAKIA.....491

UDK:616.711-007.1-073

KODIROV Umid Arzikulovich
ABDURAKHIMOV Mukhiddin
Samarkand State Medical University

RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CHRONIC BRUCELLIOSIS

For citation: Kodirov A. Umid, abdurakhimov Mukhiddin. Results of clinical and neurological indications in patients with lumbar spine dorsopathy in chronic brucellosis // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 2, pp. 262-268

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11300932>

ABSTRACT

The constant increase in the incidence of brucellosis is becoming a global problem in the world. Under our control, 35 patients with peripheral nervous system damage accompanied by pain in chronic brucellosis made up this group, of which 20 (57%) were women and 15 (43 %) men. The monitoring of the obtained data showed that the largest percentage corresponds to the rural population with livestock. The food method, in which the infection is transmitted by eating raw milk, home-made cheese and meat that has not been well thermally processed, and by keeping animals at home, in the process of animal care and in the process of cleaning buildings. Humans have been exposed to additional factors such as dust and germs while tending animals in livestock farms.

Key words: Hedderson's agglutination reaction, Rayt's agglutination reaction, brucellosis, chronic dorsopathy, osteochondrosis, chronic pain.

КОДИРОВ Умид Арзикулович
АБДУРАХИМОВ Мухиддин

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КЛИНИКО-НЕЙРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАНИЙ У БОЛЬНЫХ С ДОРСОПАТИЕЙ ПОЯСНИЧНОГО ОТДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОЗВОНОЧНИКА ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ БРУЦЕЛЛИОЗЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Постоянный рост заболеваемости бруцеллезом становится глобальной проблемой в мире. Под нашим контролем эту группу составили 35 больных с поражением периферической нервной системы, сопровождающимся болями при хроническом бруцеллезе, из них 20 (57%) женщин и 15 (43 %) мужчины. Мониторинг полученных данных показал, что наибольший процент приходится на сельское население, имеющее домашний скот. Пищевой путь, при котором инфекция передается при употреблении в пищу сырого молока, домашнего сыра и мяса, не

подвергнутого хорошей термической обработке, а также при содержании животных в домашних условиях, в процессе ухода за животными и в процессе уборки помещений. Люди подвергаются воздействию дополнительных факторов, таких как пыль и микробы, когда ухаживают за животными на животноводческих фермах.

Ключевые слова: Реакция агглютинации Хеддельсона, реакция агглютинации Райта, бруцеллез, хроническая дорсопатия, остеохондроз, хроническая боль

KODIROV Umid Arzikulovich
ABDURAXIMOV Muxiddin
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

SURUNKALI BRUSELLOYZDA BEL UMURTQALARI DORSOPATIYA BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA KLINIK VA NEVROLOGIK KO'RSATKICHLARNING NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Brutsellyoz bilan kasallanishning muttasil ortib borishi jahonda global muammoga aylanib bormoqda. Bizning nazoratimiz ostida surunkali brutsellyozda og'riq bilan kechadigan periferik asab tizimining shikastlanishi bilan og'rigan 35 nafar bemor bu guruhni tashkil etdi, ulardan 20 (57%) - ayollar va 15 (43%) erkaklar. Olingan ma'lumotlarning monitoringi shuni ko'rsatdiki, eng katta foiz chorva mollari bo'lgan qishloq aholisiga to'g'ri keladi. Ovqatlanish usuli, bunda infeksiya xom sut, uyda tayyorlangan pishloq va yaxshi termik ishlov berilmagan go'shtni iste'mol qilish va uyda hayvonlarni parvarish qilish orqali, hayvonlarni parvarish qilish jarayonida va binolarni tozalash jarayonida yuqqan. Molxonalarda hayvonlarni parvarish qilish paytida odamlar chang va mikroba kabi omillarning qo'shimcha ta'siriga duchor bo'lishdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xedderson aglutinatsiya reaksiyasi, Rayt agglyutinatsiya reaksiyasi, brutsellyoz, surunkali dorsiopatiya, osteoxondroz, surunkali og'riq.

Kirish. Umurtqa pog'onasi ildizlarining chiqishi sohasida, bel-dumg'aza va yonbosh suyagi soxasida doimiy, xarakat cheklovchi har kuni bezovta qiladigan og'riq, umumiy zaiflik va doimiy bosh og'rig'i bilan birga keladi. Surunkali og'riq tipik mushak-skeletlari topildi. Anamnezdan: bemorlar - o'z chorva mollari bo'lgan qishloq aholisi, shuningdek, xom sut, uy pishloq va termik qayta ishlanmagan go'shtni iste'mol qiladigan odamlarda mavjud.

Tadqiqot usullari: Surunkali brutsellyozning klinik diagnostikasi qon tekshiruvi bo'lib, barcha bemorlarda ijobiy Rayt agglyutinatsiya reaksiyasi va ijobiy Xedderson aglutinatsiya reaksiyasi aniqlangan - 35 (100%), shu asosda bemorlar tanlab olindi. 2-guruhdagi barcha o'rganilgan bemorlarda titr ko'rsatkichlari ijobiy natijani ko'rsatdi.

1-rasm. Bemorlarning jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi

Biz kasallikning davomiyligini ham tahlil qildik, bu o'rtacha 1 yil 11 oyni tashkil etdi. Quyidagi 2-rasmda bemorlarning ikkinchi guruhining qo'zg'atuvchi omillari sanab o'tilgan.

2- rasm. Dorsopatiyalarni qo'zg'atuvchi asosiy omillar

Tadqiqot natijalari: Umumiy obektiv axvoli: bemorlarning umumiy ahvoli nisbatan qoniqarli, ongi ravshan, xarakati passiv. Obyektiv ravishda terapevt maslahati va fizik tekshiruv vaqtida nafas olish tezligi daqiqasida 16 dan 28 martagacha, o'rtacha 21,7 va puls - 68 dan 86 gacha o'rtacha daqiqasida 76,6 zarba o'zgarganligi aniqlandi.. Ko'pincha qo'lتيq ostidagi limfa tugunlarining kattalashishi kuzatildi. Teri nam, terlash bor. Mushak-skelet tizimining qo'pol deformatsiyasi kuzatilmadi. Nafas olish organlari tomonidan patologiya aniqlanmagan. Yurak tonlari bo'g'iq. Ovqat hazm qilish organlari tomonidan yengil gepatolienal sindrom kuzatildi. Ko'pgina bemorlarda buyraklar pielonefritga moyil bo'ladi.

3-rasm. Bemorlarda surunkali og'riqni lokalizatsiya qilish

Bizning tadqiqotimizda barcha bemorlarning asosiy shikoyatlari umumiy zaiflik - 35 (100%), doimiy bosh og'rig'i - 35 (100%), kamroq bo'yindagi og'riqni qo'llarga tarqalishi - 4 (16,7%), va ko'pincha tos suyaklari sohasida og'riqlar, son va pastki oyoq mushaklarigacha cho'zilgan -12 (48%). Og'riq bemorni har kuni bezovta qiladi, xarakatni cheklaydi, 3 oydan ortiq davom etadi. Bel-dumg'aza mintaqadagi og'riqlar o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega edi: umurtqa pog'onasi ildizlarining chiqishi sohasidagi og'riqlardan tashqari, bemorlar bel-dumg'aza sinartroz va yonbosh suyagi sohasidagi og'riqni qayd etdilar.

Ayniqsa, bemorlar pastki oyoqdagi mushak og'rig'idan 6 (24%) va son -7 (28%) shikoyat qildi. 13 (52%) bemor - nevropatik og'riqlardan shikoyat qildi.

4-rasm. Bemorlarda asosiy shikoyatlarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi

Bemorlarning taxminan yarmi 17 (48,5%) bemorga noqulaylik tug'diradigan ko'p terlashdan shikoyat qilgan va 15 (42,8%) bemorda uyqusizlik, 22 (62,8%) tasida shishgan limfa tugunlari aniqlangan. Ta'sirlangan mushaklar sohasidagi sezgirlikning pasayishi 8 (22,8%) bemorda, paresteziya - 11 (31,42%), 12 (34,3%) bemorda reflekslarning pasayishi kuzatildi.

Sezuvchanlikni to'liq tekshirish bel-dumg'aza mintaqada og'riq va taktill sezuvchanlikning pasayishini aniqladi, ammo tebranish, mushak-artikulyar sezuvchanlik va bosim va massa hissi saqlanib qoldi. Aniq parez aniqlanmadi, ammo bemorlar bel-dumg'aza mintaqada cheklangan harakatni his qilishadi. Mushaklar kuchi saqlanib qoladi, 4+ ball, lekin tezda tugaydi.

Bemorlarning ushbu guruhidagi qiziqarli fakt quyosh chigalidagi og'riqni aniqlash bo'lib, bu 11 (31%) bemorda aniqlangan. Klinik va biokimyoviy qon testlari, siydik tahlillari va leykoformulaning ko'payishi shaklida yallig'lanish belgilarining hodisalarini aniqladi.

Ultratovush tekshiruvida 14 (40%) bemorda gepatosplenomegaliya aniqlangan, bu surunkali brutselloz bilan og'rikan bemorlarga juda xosdir. Surunkali brutsellyozning osteoxondroz bilan kombinatsiyasini aniqlash qiziq fakt bo'lib, unda bu ikki kasallik bir-birini og'irlashtirib, bemorning ahvolini yomonlashtirdi. Shu bilan birga, rentgenda osteoxondroz belgilari osteofitlar, qo'shma bo'shliqning torayishi va sariq ligamentdagi degenerativ o'zgarishlar edi.

30 (85,7%) bemorga umurtqa pog'onasi rentgenografiyasi o'tkazildi, unda surunkali brutsellyozli bemorlarga xos bo'lgan degenerativ-distروفik o'zgarishlar aniqlandi, ularning asosiylari: suyak to'qimalarining rezorbsiyasi subxondral o'choqlari; bo'g'im yuzalar konturlarining xiralashishi; ikkilamchi o'sishlar; fiziologik lordozni to'g'rilanishi.

5 (14,3%) bemorga MRT va MSKT tekshiruvi o'tkazildi, unda surunkali brutsellyozga xos o'zgarishlar aniqlandi.

5-rasm. Bemorlarning neyrovizual tadqiqotlari natijalari

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, bu guruhdagi bemorlarni klinik va nevrologik tekshirish natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, umurtqa pog'onasi ildizlarining chiqishi sohasida, bel-dumg'aza va yonbosh suyagi soxasida doimiy, xarakat cheklovchi har kuni bezovta qiladigan og'riq, umumiy zaiflik va doimiy bosh og'rig'i bilan birga keladi. Surunkali og'riq tipik mushak-skeletlari topildi. Anamnezdan: bemorlar - o'z chorva mollari bo'lgan qishloq aholisi, shuningdek, xom sut, uy pishloq va termik qayta ishlanmagan go'shtni iste'mol qiladigan odamlarda mavjud. Boshqa guruhlar uchun xarakterli shikoyat epigastral mintaqada og'riqning mavjudligi edi. Bemorlar, shuningdek, pastki oyoq va sondagi neyropatik mushak og'rig'i, bemor uchun noqulaylik tug'diradigan ko'p terlash, uyqusizlik, limfa tugunlarining shishishi, ta'sirlangan mushaklar sohasidagi sezgirlikning pasayishi, paresteziya, reflekslarning pasayishi.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. – vol. 7. – No. 6. (in Russ)
2. Khakimova S.Z., Atokhodjaeva D.A., Hamrokulova F.M. Research Of Motor Function In Patients With Chronic Pain Syndrome At Radiculopathies Of Different Genesis. The American Journal of Applied sciences, 2020. 2 (10), 14-21.
3. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.O. Comparative correlation of markers of inflammatory metamorphism in peripheral blood in dorsopathies of various origins //Uzbek journal of case reports. – 2022. 2(2). 12-18. (in Russ).
4. Samiyev A.S, Xakimova S.X, Soibnazarov O.E. Rehabilitation of patients under spine surger. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022;7(1):139-44.
5. Utkurovna S.G., Farkhodovna, K.F., Orifjonovna O.F, Features of immune mechanisms in the development of pathological processes,2022 ,2 (82), 108-115.
6. Axmedova D.A., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Features of post-stroke depression in the early and late recovery periods" Innovative Science, 2015, 6(2), 224-227 (in Russ).
7. Burieva D.M., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Comparative study of the function of maintaining a vertical posture in healthy foxes and patients with parkinsonism" Innovative science, 2015. 6(2) 232-236 (in Russ).

8. Dadasheva M.N., Razilova A.V., Boldin A.V. Possibilities of practical use of dexketoprofen in pain syndrome of various etiologies. 2018. 16(10),32–36. (in Uzb).
9. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice.2022.7(6). (in Russ).
10. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.A. Features of clinical and neurological results of examination of patients with dorsopathies of rheumatic origin // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. 7(1). (in Russ).
11. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B. K., Kodirov U.A. Study of motor function in patients with chronic pain syndrome with dorsopathies of various origins // tools, mechanisms and technologies of modern innovative development. – 2022. 243-251. (in Russ).
12. Khakimova S.Z. Chronic brucellosis in the real practice of a neurologist: (clinical diagnosis and treatment). Benefits of clinical and experimental medicine, 2019;1 (3), 133–138. (in Russ).
13. Sh Shakhonova , N Rakhimov, B Esankulova , F Koraboev , A Khakimov. Complications of targeted therapy in the treatment of renal cell cancer with metastases to the bones and lymph nodes . Journal of the Doctor's Bulletin 2021, Volume 1, Number 2 (99), P116-120.
14. Rizaev , Zh., Raimova , M., Boboev , K., & Abdullaeva, M. (2019). Parkinson's: classification, clinical picture and basics of treatment. Stomatologiya , 1(1(74), 64–67

Статья поступила в редакцию 06.03.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 20.04.2024; принята к публикации 26.04.2024.

The article was submitted 06.03.2024; approved after reviewing 20.04.2024; accepted for publication 26.04.2024.

Информация об авторах:

Абдурахимов Мухиддин- Клинический ординатор кафедры неврологии факультета последипломного образования Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, Самарканд, Узбекистан. <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1902-4491>

Кодиров Умид Арзикулович — ассистент кафедры неврологии факультета последипломного образования Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, Самарканд, Узбекистан <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9671-3288>

Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Абдурахимов М.— сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Кодиров У А. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Abdurakhimov Mukhiddin-clinical ordinator of the department of neurology, faculty of postgraduate education, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1902-4491>

Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich — teacher at the department of neurology of the faculty of postgraduate education of Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9671-3288>

Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Abdurakhimov M— collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

Kodirov U A — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000